

Distinction by indistinction: luxury, stealth, minimalist fashion

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ABSTRACT: Setting out from the Simmelian premise that fashion is the site of tension between conformity and distinction, this essay enquires into the element of distinction heightened in minimalist luxury fashion. Minimalist luxury reveals the inherently divisive nature of fashion, putting distance between “us”—the nonchalant, productive, and moral—and “them”—the vulgar, useless, and amoral. Its seeming austerity is an effective mechanism of status assertion, highlighting fashion as a continual cycle of exclusion. The essay examines the class-, gender-, and race-bias implicated in minimalist luxury, before using Martin Margiela’s contrasting practice at Maison Martin Margiela and at Hermès as one case in which the ideals of minimalist luxury are strategically exploited. The case of Margiela also underscores the challenge luxury fashion faces as digital mediation increasingly prioritizes fashion as a visual, rather than material, practice. Digital mediation facilitates the global diffusion of the minimalist aesthetic, dividing the world into mythical classes according to taste, which supports Simmel’s idea of fashion and its potential pertinence to wider intercultural relations.

KEYWORDS: minimalist fashion; stealth luxury; Martin Margiela; othering; classism; adornment.

Distinction by indistinction: luxury, stealth, minimalist fashion

In a 1951 article published in *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism*, Robert L. Steiner and Joseph Weiss observed a new prestige scheme emerging in post-war America. This new scheme relied on the consumption of exorbitantly priced goods that appeared, at first glance, to be ordinary and simple. Because the scheme was easily adopted by the old elite yet difficult for the new rich to grasp, it was used by the old elite to perpetuate superiority over the “nouveau”. Whereas the new rich (the “snobs”) follow the pattern of conspicuous consumption (Veblen 2007), the old elite (the “counter-snobs”) make apparent their indifference to such ostentatious display. By masquerading their nonchalance, the old elite maintain their social prestige over those with “wrong” taste and “wrong” origins. Steiner and Weiss (1951, pp. 263–67) thus see this seeming austerity as an “inverse-exhibitionism ... quite as flagrant as the pomp and circumstance of former years”. Such inverse-exhibitionism was iterated in twentieth-century Western fashion: for instance, it was named “minimalism” in the early 1980s and “stealth power-dressing” (Mower 2010) in the 1990s. In the twenty-first century this style or attitude is more widespread globally, functioning as a visual cue for either out-of-reach luxury or its budget imitations.

Many of the adjectives often used to describe this style—“austere,” “pared down,” “discreet,” “restrained,” “pure,” “quiet” and “understated”—also apply to the qualities often sought in many religious contexts as a way to practice modesty, generosity or tolerance in everyday life. The style of minimalist fashion, however, appears to be an effective form of status assertion for perpetuating a prestige system, focusing more on exclusion than inclusion, although these are two sides of the same coin. This stratagem aims to achieve distinction by indistinction, via dressing down in “everyday essentials” or “easy basics,” avoiding ornamentation and the polychrome. It often takes an overt anti-fashion stance, praising “classic” or “timeless” pieces. Above all, the look must appear effortless, as if “just thrown together”. This air of nonchalance is consistent with the marketing strategies of some luxury brands which, seemingly, do not even exist. This includes blank-page magazine or email

advertisements, stores without signage, logo-free shopping bags and resistance to markdowns. When successful, these forms of indistinction create the aura of distinction and exclusiveness, the essential markers of luxury and class.

The English word “class” originates from the Latin word *classis*, the civic classes of the Roman people, which was introduced in 6BCE. Although this division according to status, wealth and age created five categories, the word was especially associated with its highest category. (Partridge 2006, p. 525) This is also the case in today’s use of the term: the adjective “classic” is linked to the highest quality of its kind; used in relation to a design, it refers to simple, elegant and timeless style. When we say colloquially that someone or something “has class,” the connotation is invariably positive. The meaning of the supposedly neutral word becomes value-laden when it is associated with categorizing or ordering. For sociologist Georg Simmel, style and class are intrinsically linked. The essence of social life is the struggle between individuality and generality, and style—as in a stylized costume, form of life, taste—arises as the result of this struggle. (Simmel 1991, p.69) To have or be of a certain style means that the particularity of the individual is subjugated to a general law of form that also applies to others (ibid., p.64). Style is thus more general or typical than purely individual, implying a certain type, class or group (ibid., p.67). That people can articulate their class through consumption is because the sense of distinction is affirmed in their stylistic or thematic choices (Bourdieu 1984, p.502). By choosing to dress or behave in a certain way, we put a *distance* between ourselves and others. Style, then, is intrinsically divisive. It both categorizes and is a product of categorization. It can be said that fashion is the constant and complex operations of othering and exclusion through shifting choices of style. This becomes evident when Steiner and Weiss (1951, p.267) acknowledge the presence of “counter-counter-snobs” and so on in the context of 1950s America, as discussed above.

Throughout the Western fashions of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries, the plain surfaces of inverse-exhibitionism repeatedly classified tastes and styles into “in” or “out”, “right” or “wrong”. The following text first examines the class-bias implicated in minimalist fashion by tracing its possible origin via the use of the term “vulgar”. If we postulate that Western fashion was

prompted by industrialization and democratization, this section reveals the classism inherent in fashion. The second section addresses the built-in gender-bias of minimalist style. Having adopted the standardized male look for greater physical, social and political freedom, women in the twenty-first century still need to conform to minimalist ideals—the now-invisible but still dominant dress-code—to be taken seriously. The third section aligns minimalist fashion with modernist architecture and its race-bias marked on its whitewashed walls. The final section takes the practice of Martin Margiela as one case in which the mechanism of minimalist fashion is strategically exploited, by comparing the stealth luxury of Hermès and the grittiness displayed at Maison Martin Margiela. The essay concludes by tracing the trajectory of minimalist luxury fashion in the twenty-first century, how it standardizes and gentrifies global taste, fictitiously classifying the world into the minimalist rich and the decorative rest.

Becoming in/distinct: the terror of vulgarity

In his 1899 publication *The Theory of the Leisure Class*, Thorstein Veblen (2007, pp.111–14) analyzes how affluent American societies articulated their status through consumption. In particular, clothes were intended to reveal their socio-economic standing at first glance via the principles of “conspicuous waste,” “conspicuous leisure” and “novelty”. In other words, the costliness of outfits suggested that the wearer can consume in excess of what is necessary; and fashionable yet uncomfortable garments communicated that the wearer does not need to engage in useful labor to earn a living, that he or she can consume without producing. However, as the wealthy leisure class had grown so large during the preceding one hundred years, Veblen suggests, these indices were “replaced by other, more delicate methods of expressing the same fact; methods which are no less evident to the trained eyes of that smaller, select circle whose good opinion is chiefly sought.” (ibid., p.123) Such delicate maneuvers ensured that “the baser elements of the population” were excluded from the scheme (ibid.). This tendency, Veblen observes, was especially apparent in the development of men’s clothing.

In Europe, men's clothing became almost standardized as an austere style at the end of the eighteenth century. Psychoanalyst John Carl Flügel (1940, pp.110–12) designates this change as the “Great Masculine Renunciation.” Many of Flügel's contemporaries considered the French Revolution to be the main cause of the “sudden reduction of male sartorial decorativeness”. The new social ideals that found expression in the Revolution—liberty, equality, fraternity—rendered the elaborate costume of the *ancien régime* distasteful, leading to a greater uniformity as well as simplification of dress. Moreover, with the democratic forces of the Revolution, gentlemen “hoped to escape the guillotine by looking as bourgeois as possible” (William Ralph Inge cited in Bourke 1996, p.24). This type of adaptation, or disguise, was felt useful again at the end of the 1920s, when it was feared that “the unfortunate capitalist, reduced to bury his bond notes instead of investing, may find it expedient to try to pass for a trade unionist” (ibid.). The motivation behind stealthy male appearances, then, was to become less remarkable or less distinct in the unsettled social, economic and political atmosphere. As a result, in the seemingly classless and timeless men's suit, the distinction or “production of the ‘distinguished’ man” (Barthes 2005, p.63) had to rely on nonchalance, all the while paying punctilious attention to details and nuances. It was of course the dandy who perfected the balance between feigned nonchalance and exquisiteness. Charles Baudelaire (1964, p.28), writing in 1863, emphasizes that dandyism appears in periods of transition and disorder, when aristocracy is being replaced by democracy.

This points to another main cause of this standardization, as briefly touched on above in the American setting. In eighteenth-century Western Europe, thanks to technological advances and the growth of international trading and mercantile capitalism, more luxury goods and materials became available than ever before. As more people were able to afford luxury goods, the people of “good society” resorted to “subtler contrivances” to distinguish themselves from “the untrained sensibilities of the vulgar” (Veblen 2007, pp.123–24). For the existing elite, psychoanalyst Adam Phillips (2016, p.59) writes, “the other terror, in the century of the French Revolution, was the terror of vulgarity.” Good taste thus had to be over-refined and over-protected.

Fashion played a prominent part in this conscious and/or unconscious act of exclusion. Phillips (ibid., p.11) suggests that the evolving meaning of the word “vulgar” reflects the socio-economic backdrop of eighteenth- and nineteenth-century England. Since the eighteenth century, the neutral meaning of the word (“common or customary in respect of the use or understanding of language, words, or ideas”) was replaced by value-laden ones: “a person not reckoned as belonging to good society,” “not refined or advanced beyond the common” or “lacking in refinement or good taste.” (ibid.) The current meanings of the term, then, are the product of inverse-exhibitionism, and to use the word is itself to engage in the operation of othering. It dissociates “us” from “them”, revealing our fear of being indistinct, indistinguishable, “nothing special.” (ibid., p.59)

Whether someone or something is “refined” or “vulgar” is, of course, contingent on time, place and social setting. “Counter-counter-snobs” would certainly sneer at the vulgarity of “counter-snobs.” The way in which the constant process of exclusion perpetuates change resembles how fashion is propelled forward by its own denial: fashion is unthinkable outside of the resistance to it. (Wigley 2001, p.xxiii) The history of fashion is the institutionalized rejection of the fashions of last season, of the too popular, of the vulgar. To put it differently, fashion is the result of the oscillation between adaptation to our social group (imitation, conformity) and individual elevation from it (distinction, change) (Simmel 1997, pp.187–89). Even a conscious display of *disinterest* in fashion or an anti-fashion attitude is an aspect of fashion, “just as atheism has been made into a religion, embodying the same fanaticism, the same intolerance [...] embraced in religion” (ibid., p.195). Both minimalist and anti-fashion stances pursue the absolute, the last word, the final judgement, which may be a “timeless” style or a total rejection of style. It is the seeming renunciation of fashion that unites the two, as they un/knowingly participate in the endless cycle of exclusion.

Becoming useful: female dandies and anti-fashion style

Conspicuous anti-fashion attitudes are often accompanied by a strong emphasis on morality and work ethic. For instance, the Facebook founder Mark Zuckerberg (cited in Friedman 2018) commented that he wears his daily

uniform of plain gray T-shirts (by Brunello Cucinelli), because “I really want to clear my life to make it so that I have to make as few decisions as possible about anything except how to best serve this community.” [Figure 1] A similar comment came from Elizabeth Holmes (the founder of now defunct start-up Theranos),¹ whose daily uniform of a black turtleneck top (by Issey Miyake) was well-known: “It makes it easy, because every day you put on the same thing and don't have to think about it ... All my focus is on the work. I take it so seriously; I'm sure that translates into how I dress.” (Leive 2015) Such polarization of fashion and productivity (and morality) may also originate from the time of the French Revolution when the ideal men's place moved from decorative drawing-rooms to offices where useful activities take place. Their simple and uniform suits projected the commercial ideals of the time and the associated work ethic. (Flügel 1940, pp.111–13) A dandy's fanatic commitment to fashion and a “serious” industrialist's anti-fashion attitude were both responses to the same socio-economic background. This combination of adaptation, disguise and mimicry met the female body in the twentieth century via the female dandies of 1920s Europe.

As bourgeois male clothing became standardized at the end of the eighteenth century, it was the task of the woman to consume vicariously for her husband or her father and display their status. His inconspicuous suit provided the ideal background for her fashionable appearance (Vinken 1999, p.37). By the principal of “conspicuous leisure,” it was necessary for the wearer's comfort to be disregarded, and for the garment to be impractical. Veblen (2007, p.122) thus conjectures that the corset was more popular in the period of snobbery—the interval of uncertainty and of transition from the lower to the upper levels of consumption. At the same time, the political ideals of the French Revolution also initiated various dress reform movements in nineteenth-century Europe and the US (Cunningham 2003). By the 1910s, the agitation for women's political and social equality heightened, rejecting Victorian fashions that symbolically and literally restricted women's mobility (Fields 2007, pp.47–48). As women's access to physical and social activities grew, the demand for less restrictive garments and lighter corsets increased (ibid., p.50), leading to the first twentieth-century example of a minimalist aesthetic in the 1920s.

Jean Patou's pleated knee-length skirt and sleeveless top, designed for the tennis player Suzanne Lenglen (1926), exemplified the new sensibility enabled by greater social and physical freedom. Likewise, the leisure- and resort-wear worn by British and European elites had looser lines with simpler types of fastening such as zips and snaps instead of buttons or lacing. Gabrielle Chanel, one of Patou's contemporaries, first started out by making elaborate hats for the mistresses upon whom upper class or bourgeois socialite men displayed their wealth. But it was when she transferred dandy masculinity onto the female bodies of affluent seaside resorts that she secured an enduring influence in fashion. The blazers, trousers, skirt-and-jacket suits that Chanel designed in the 1920s and 1930s have since become often-quoted "fashion classics." This status may only have been possible due to the fact that this style was inherited from—productive, authentic and moral—men.

The T-shirt is another classic menswear item in the contemporary female stealth luxury wardrobe. It was already a fashionable everyday item among 1950s American men, but became a hyper-luxury womenswear item in the late 1970s, in the American designer Zoran Ladicorbic's capsule collections. His plain yet fine cashmere T-shirts were in muted colors, produced in a single size with a relaxed line. Zoran is a significant node of minimalist fashion, connecting 1920s sportswear with the luxury capsule wardrobes increasingly popular today.² Its stealth approach is captured by the epithets awarded by the fashion press—"the Mies van der Rohe of clothing" (Menkes 1993); "The Wizard of Ease" (Vogue 1983); "Gap for the very rich" (Horyn 1999). This strict minimalist aesthetic evolved amid the excess of the mid-1980s, with a Japanese influence—especially Yohji Yamamoto and Rei Kawakubo, whose deconstructive approaches and monochromatic designs paved the way for the decade of minimalist fashion. In the 1990s, Calvin Klein, Donna Karan, Helmut Lang, Jil Sander and many others popularized the style of "stealth power-dressing" (Mower 2010), which emphasized the status of career women, albeit in a much subtler way than did the 1980s power-dressing.³ If Jil Sander's restrained style masked 1990s women's aspiration for status and power (Arnold 2000, p.170), the reason for its effectiveness may lie, as pointed out above, in the style's male origin and its related female mimicry in the 1920s. A twenty-

first century woman must continue to emulate the minimal, thus “masculine,” style in order to be taken seriously. Women can enjoy greater equality and respect insofar as they dress like men, dissociated from decoration or adornment. This is also broadly the case across cultures that only those who emulate the look of *Western men* may be taken seriously. Minimalist fashion reveals the process through which female or male qualities are reinforced, prompting us to rethink the power relationship embedded in the still-dominant dress-code. [Figure 2]

The plain surface of minimalist fashion, however, is still adorned. It may not bear any visible logo, precious material or embroidery, but it is still adornment—subtractive adornment—in the sense that Simmel proposes. For Simmel (1950, p.338), adornment is not necessarily decorative, but something that functions similarly as secrecy or disguise. Like the divisive and typifying nature of Simmelian “style”, this type of adornment marks the *distance* between the adorned and the viewer. (ibid., p.342)

Subtractive adornment

The minimalist luxury of contemporary dandyism excels in projecting an air of nonchalance, meticulously perfecting a relaxed look. As one fashion journalist writes: “there’s far more involved than plain undecorated clothes; when you’re making choices of minute degree, a miss is as good as a total embarrassment” (Mower 2010). This catastrophic failure, of course, is only detectable by trained and discerning eyes, as cultural historian Jonathan Faiers (2017, p.187) piquantly puts it: “real luxury should remain unrecognisable by the masses, signalling its status only to a very select group who can identify and appreciate the wearer’s sartorial connoisseurship.” In the order of stealth luxury, secrecy and display are thus inseparably linked. It is a form of disguise, an invisible display, a secret insignia which creates rank. It proves that “luxury still determines the rank of the one who displays it, and there is no exalted rank that does not require a display.” (Bataille 1988, p.76)

Therefore, the “muted” surface of minimalist luxury is not silent. Literary semiologist Roland Barthes (2005, p.24) muses that a person’s silence has a “speechly substance” in human interaction. Our silence implicates. Standing in

for the wearer, the plain surface congeals itself into a sign, into “a polyvalent weapon” (ibid., p.24, p.27). It performs an operation of othering, by surveilling and excluding “wrong” tastes.

The idea of exclusive access and limited edition relies on a sense of entitlement. In the seventeenth century, handwritten poems were often valued more highly than poems in print, especially by those who believed that poetry should only be accessible to a particular group. This limited access protected its value, or rather, its value was contingent on the restrictiveness. (Phillips 2016, p.13) Here, Phillips senses a fear: like the plague, the vulgar touches and infects the poetry, killing its aura. “There is the vulgar, the printed, the common, the infectious, the unwholesome: and there is the poetry, the manuscript, [that] only the refined and the fashionable should have access to.” (ibid., p.14) Although fashion always unites connection and differentiation with its “double function of holding a given social circle together and at the same time closing it off from others” (Simmel 1997, p.189), what is accentuated in minimalist or stealth style is the function of closing off. To be distinguished is to possess good judgement, to possess *discerning* eyes (from the Latin *dis-* “apart” + *cernere* “to separate”), of which the function is to divide and exclude.

A parallel example may be drawn from the polemics surrounding the whitewashing of modern architecture. The austerity of modern architecture was a reaction against the decorative surfaces of nineteenth-century buildings. Adolf Loos’s infamous essay “Ornament and Crime” (1908) condemns the *Jugendstil* as “degenerate” and “regressive”, propagating the virtue of “neutral”, “pure”, “silent”, “plain”, “essential” surfaces. Taking this even further, in the International Style, the whole moral, ethical, functional, technical superiority of modern architecture hangs on the whiteness of its austere walls (Wigley 2001). Following Loos, Le Corbusier regards civilization as “a gradual passage from the sensual to the intellectual, from the tactile to the visual”. (Wigley 2001, p.3) The architecture of the civilized West, therefore, must reject the sensuousness of decoration and strive for pure visual abstraction. In *L’art décoratif d’aujourd’hui* (1925) Le Corbusier writes: “The white of whitewash is absolute: everything stands out from it and is recorded absolutely, black on white ... Put on it anything dishonest or in bad taste—it hits you in the eye.” (ibid., p.8)

Architect Mark Wigley therefore considers the whitewash as a kind of “surveillance device looking for small flaws, traces of decorative play” (ibid., p.42). Influenced by the social mood of the time, Le Corbusier sets austere male clothing as the exemplar of intellectual and pure design: “Decoration [is] suited to simple races, peasants and savages. ... The peasant loves ornament and decorates his walls. The civilized man wears a well-cut suit and is the owner of easel pictures and books.” (ibid., p.16) Some seventy years later, past the peak of 1990s minimalist fashion, artist Douglas Coupland (1997, p.82) derides such policing of “good” taste, also via the example of men’s suit: “Armanism: After Giorgio Armani: an obsession with mimicking the seamless and (more importantly) controlled ethos of Italian couture. Like Japanese Minimalism, Armanism reflects a profound inner need for control.”⁴ The surface of minimalist fashion is anything but neutral: it is marked by the purifying stains of surveillance operation. Purity of surface “makes distinctions, draws lines, classifies, making certain things stand out as other, rendering them as other, so that they can be patronized or removed.” (Wigley 2001, p.361) Just like the use of the term “vulgar”, the whitewash is a form of defense against the infection of “wrong” taste, “inappropriate” class, against inclusion.

Le Corbusier’s triumphal narrative of modernist architecture was inspired by the supposed whiteness of classical architecture. However, his antecedent Gottfried Semper had already embraced the existence of decoration and polychromy in classical architecture and sculpture. Although it is a well-established fact that Ancient Greek architecture and sculptures were colorfully adorned, it is still a popular myth that their sophisticated taste must have preferred white undecorated surfaces. It was in fact only in the beginning of the fifteenth century that the Roman and Florentine masters created unpainted “classical” architecture and sculpture (Semper [1834] 2010, pp.54–56). Semper (ibid., pp.59–60) argues that polychrome ornamentation was natural and necessary for the Greeks, as it was a part of living with the bright southern light and strongly tinted landscape. When faced with numerous painted traces visible on archeological fragments, critics, unwilling to accept that “the *Greeks* could have been so tasteless,” assign them to a more “barbaric” time and culture (ibid. p.59, italics in the original). The classism permeating the arguments against

polychromy is also present in minimalist fashion, and is a reminder of Steiner and Weiss's (1951, p.265) assertion that "the concept of counter-snobbery can apply to an old established but challenged nation in its dealings with other countries."

Martin Margiela's minimalism

The trajectory of minimalist fashion examined above leads to the practice of one designer in particular. Martin Margiela explored and exploited the mechanism of stealth luxury both at Maison Martin Margiela and at Hermès as its womenswear creative director (1997–2003, 12 consecutive collections).⁵ Converging in Margiela's body of work are 1920s sportswear, Zoran's stealth luxury (since the late 1970s), Rei Kawakubo's work for Comme des Garçons (1980s),⁶ 1990s minimalism, and more recent brands such as Celine by Phoebe Philo (2008–2017) and The Row (2006–).⁷

During his twenty years of activity as a fashion designer (1988–2008), Margiela reflexively responded to the work of his contemporaries as well as his own. The press-release for Margiela's first collection for Hermès states the theme of "nonchalance" and the influence of 1920s sportswear and leisure wear (Debo 2018, p.39). Throughout the 1990s, Margiela consistently examined how the nonchalance of minimalism was produced and performed. As a result of taking apart and subverting this ideal at his own label, I would suggest, he was able to stage the quintessence of minimalist luxury in the French house. Just as the Japanese minimalist aesthetic contrasts highly with cramped everyday Japanese city living,⁸ the stealth luxury of Hermès is even more distinctive when juxtaposed with its obverse, the gritty reality displayed at the Maison.

Also significant is that Hermès's appointment of Margiela in 1997 introduced elements of "intellect" to the notion of luxury, thereby deepening the polarization of fashion (decorative, frivolous) and anti-fashion (plain, work, serious). Although many high-fashion designers capitalized on the snobbism of "intellectual fashion" in the 1990s, the effect was perhaps greater when Hermès—representing the ideal of French tradition and wealth, typically associated with aristocratic items such as saddlery and decorative scarves—adopted such an attitude. Notably, Margiela made the symbolic gesture of

removing the image of a horse-drawn carriage on its logo and buttons, replacing it with plain designs. [Figure 3] The appointment thus produced an effective form of inverse-exhibitionism.

Moreover, in the late 1990s many European fashion houses were embracing extravagant shows and star designers with cult-like followings.⁹ Margiela's branding, by contrast, relied on invisibility or the impression of anonymity. Hermès's marketing strategy, similar to that of Zoran's in the early 1980s, focused on enhancing the aura of exclusivity by resisting markdown, avoiding licensing deals, and controlling its exposure both in advertising and product availability. The idiosyncratic match of Margiela with Hermès, therefore, created a powerful image of distinction. It could be argued that these tendencies of inverse-exhibitionism have intensified in more recent luxury brands. The great expansion of the internet and the widespread use of smartphones since the 2000s heralded new platforms of visibility, increasing fashion marketing's reliance on celebrities. This enhanced visibility also exacerbated issues of the counterfeit, while the excessive consumption patterns of the rich were broadcast ever more conspicuously on digital platforms.¹⁰ These changes may have triggered some luxury brands to distance themselves from such over-exposure and mark their distinction by stealth and invisibility.

Margiela skillfully exploited the tension between the visible and the invisible, conspicuously displaying anonymity as the face of the brand. Such branding was most effectively played in the blank white label. [Figure 4a and 4b] Attached by four tacks clearly visible on the outside, the anti-brand label created a myth surrounding Margiela who refused to be shown or heard and whose models' faces were obscured on stage.¹¹ During the first few years of the Maison's inception, the four white tacks were recognized only by the "in-group", functioning like a secret password among the connoisseurs of "intellectual" fashion.¹² Elsewhere, Margiela exhaustively explored the notion of branding. One such examples was a humorous rendition of "logo-mania": all the original labels collected from reclaimed and upcycled garments were applied on the front bodice of a waistcoat.¹³ (Spring–Summer 2001) (Samson 2018, p.98)

If the blank white label exploits the principle of inverse-exhibitionism which Margiela perfected at Hermès, the white scheme of Maison Martin Margiela consciously comments on and criticizes the principle. It also evidences the Simmelian idea of fashion as the site of tension between individuality and un-individuality. In the same year as Margiela's appointment at Hermès, the Maison held its first retrospective, *La Maison Martin Margiela (9/4/1615)*, at the Museum Boijmans van Beuningen, Rotterdam (June 11–August 17, 1997) (Samson 2018, p.156).¹⁴ In terms of both materiality and visual appearance, this exhibition showed the antithesis of the subtractive adornment of the minimalist aesthetic that he was to stage at the French house. The exhibition was comprised of eighteen outfits reproduced from their previous collections, all in whites or greys. In collaboration with a microbiologist, Margiela treated each outfit with varying strains of bacteria, yeast and mold. The texture and color of the garments gradually changed as the organisms flourished, and later, withered (see te Duits 1997). The changing appearance of these garments, now inseparable from their organic decoration, seemed to show what a lived surface is really like. Another, seemingly opposite, process appeared to be inspired by the same motivation: the Maison often washed its completed outfits to remove their brand-new crispness and to make them appear more lived-in. If the act of washing was in line with the act of destroying in Rei Kawakubo's work in the 1980s, in Margiela's work the act of washing and staining were both acts of creation.

In the Rotterdam retrospective, the white or grey surfaces, like sacrificial offerings, were there exclusively to be lived in and blemished. As the obverse of the pure Hermès surfaces, the “whites” of Maison Martin Margiela exist to show off stains and scuffs. If Le Corbusier's white wall is a surveillance camera that records any deviation from its project of control, Margiela's whites luxuriate in touches and their imprints. Indeed, the whites physically and symbolically record the Maison's history: they opened the very first Maison Martin Margiela show (Spring–Summer 1989) and closed it with the studio team appearing on stage in the white lab coats traditionally worn by models between fittings. (Samson 2018, p.8) Moreover, the interior of the Maison's studio on 163 rue Saint-Maure was entirely white, including the furniture and

objects it contained. [Figure 5] Originally this choice was born out of necessity: when the Maison first started out, it could not afford new furniture. To give the interior a visual coherence, they covered various pieces of junk furniture in white paint or white cloth (Holzemer 2019). Whereas the matt-black surfaces popularized by Kawakubo and Yamamoto in the 1980s render impurities imperceptible, Margiela's whites show off daily wear. The whites thus embody the tension between the personal and the impersonal: it stylizes, in Simmel's term, the space and objects under the label, while imprints introduce subtle differences to every surface.

Margiela's whites, therefore, have a symbolic and processual affinity with his "favorite" colors, which reappear in his collections season after season. For the Spring–Summer 1991 collection, the Maison purchased 1950s ball gowns which they then dyed in a washing machine to achieve a semblance of coherence (Samson 2018, p.28). As different fabrics take black dye differently, the dresses came out in varying shades of grey. Similarly, for the following season (Fall–Winter 1991–92), Margiela made tight-fitting sweaters by putting together eight pairs of secondhand military socks. When dyed, they too came out of the washing machine in shades of green and black (ibid., p.32). [Figure 6] Following on from these two examples, the meaning of Margiela's whites becomes clear with the "White Collection" (Spring–Summer 1993), for which the studio reworked secondhand theater costumes. The outfits were then bleached in the final stage, resulting in various pastel shades (ibid., p.44). [Figure 7] White, grey, green, black, cream and pastel shades in above examples are the result of the same process. Unlike the absolute white Le Corbusier endorses, these "whites" are "the slight difference" replete with nuances (Barthes 2005, p.51). The white scheme does not aim to produce a unifying standard, but instead something incomparable and shifting.

The translation between tactile imprints and visual imprints is a process also highlighted in Margiela's use of *trompe l'oeil*. One of the most frequently used techniques at the Maison, *trompe l'œil* functions in a similar way to the whites by estranging the minimalist style and its surface. Its most well-known variation, the Spring–Summer 1996 collection, was comprised of the simplest "basics" such as the T-shirt, sheath dress and cardigan. [Figure 8a and 8b] Any

details, volume and embellishments were added in the form of greyscale photographic print, creating a visual illusion. The team photographed the front and the back of twelve found garments on a mannequin or hanger, which were then printed onto the basics. As a result, bulky and elaborate items such as a 1930s Shetland overcoat or a 1950s fur coat was converted into fluid lightweight items. (Samson 2018, p.62) The collection was minimal and ornamental at once, as if unfolding unconscious phantasies of the minimalist aesthetic. The main thesis of this collection can be glimpsed in a light satin dress printed with the photographic image of a 1960s lace dress turned inside out.¹⁵ The lining—now printed on the outside—shows the original manufacturer and size information, along with creases, seams, facings and fastenings, revealing the complex process of assembly to produce “simple” garments. Twice removed from the actual, this dress compounds the technical process behind an impeccable garment with the trained nonchalance of stealth luxury. It is thus the counterpart of refined Hermès outfits, which are often reversible with no lining or surface embellishment. Hermès performs its minimalist perfection, while Maison Martin Margiela reveals it as a disguise.

Margiela used variations of *trompe l'œil* techniques, all of which engage with the idea of subtractive adornment. For the Spring–Summer 1998 collection, a pair of jeans were presented with the belt, pockets, loops and labels removed, with their ghostly traces creating visual illusions (ibid., p.78). And for Spring–Summer 2009, Margiela traced the seams of a denim jacket using blue carbon paper and transferred the image onto a white garment (ibid., p.150). What these examples materialize is the link between old and new: the imprint of the past marks the beginning of the new. This temporal link extends to a spatial link. Before the Maison moved to a new studio on rue Saint-Maure, black-and-white photographs of the old studio – interior details such as baroque mirrors, marble mantelpieces, decorative rosettes – were taken. Reproducing the photographs on the bare walls of the new studio thus created an impression that part of the old studio was transplanted to the new one. (Debo et al. 2008)

Such deliberate yet subtle links appear to be vital in understanding the relationship between Margiela’s work at the Maison and at Hermès: his minimalist aesthetic at Hermès was not the refinement of something crude.

Instead, it was the result of having taken apart and grasped the mechanism of refinement. Via exploiting the existing paradigm—old versus new, original versus reproduction, unique versus stereotype—Margiela’s practice at the Maison reveals how the ideals of stealth luxury are constructed and performed.

The global diffusion of minimalist fashion

It is now evident that Margiela explored fashion both as visual and material practice. The whites accentuate materiality by drawing attention to the process of making and wearing while the iterations of *trompe l’oeil* technique let us question what we are really seeing. The examples above highlight how fashion is increasingly being produced for, and consumed as, visual abstraction and illusion. Margiela left the fashion industry just before digital mediation started to hegemonize it. The peculiar situation of the year 2020—where most major fashion presentations take place exclusively online—puts a fresh emphasis on the question posed more than a decade ago: Where is fashion? Fashion is at once a tactile and material practice, a visual representation, a manufacturing industry, as well as a social, cultural and commercial space. In the context of digital mediation and virtual interaction, however, fashion increasingly becomes a *visual art*. Sociologist Richard Sennett (1992, p.108) suggests that the use of transparent thermal plate glass in modern buildings isolated other senses from the optic, contributing to the dematerialization of everyday experience. When much of social interaction takes place through the computer or mobile screen, fashion is more reliant on the sense of vision, alienated from other senses, than before.

This tendency is perhaps most acutely felt in luxury fashion, traditionally the domain of personalization, face-to-face interaction and artisanal handmade production. Digital mediation allows wide access to the high-definition images of Haute Couture in real time, “democratizing” luxury. At the same time, with the global circulation and consumption of luxury as images on a digital screen, the distinction between original and copy has become blurred. In such conditions, minimalist style appears to accelerate the polarization of fashion into hyper-luxury and budget markets. For instance, the subtleties of the Hermès outfits Margiela created were out of the reach of photographic mediations. The

collections were thus presented in the label's Paris store on Rue du Faubourg Saint-Honoré to small groups of journalists sitting in a single row, so that they could appreciate the fine details of material and finishing. (Arnold 2018, p.184) The emphasis on the subtleties that could only be appreciated up-close reveals its elitist stance. On the other hand, when materiality takes a back seat, it is minimal style that can be most easily reproduced to the degree that looks indistinguishable, on the screen, from the original. Many “masstige” brands (e.g. Cuyana, Uterqüe, Massimo Dutti) and budget brands (e.g. Everlane, COS, Uniqlo) have adopted a minimalist aesthetic with clever visual marketing. As a magazine article entitled “How to look rich wearing only Uniqlo”¹⁶ shows (Petrarca 2019), a monochrome sweater on a digital screen could either be Uniqlo or Yohji Yamamoto. The ubiquity of minimalist designs on virtual spaces seems to have turned the style into the marker of “conformist anonymity”. (Arnold 2000, p.180)

Not only is the physical world consumed as digital images, but the digital image is now shaping the physical world. The diffusion of the minimalist aesthetic may have homogenized tastes across the globe. Whether this is the case or not is less consequential than the impression of it. For instance, the Weissenhof Estate—built in Stuttgart on the occasion of Deutscher Werkbund exhibition in 1927—was widely known through the mediation of black and white photography, thus establishing the idea that modern Western architecture, later known as International Style, is white, pure and intellectual, and thus superior. (Wigley 2001, pp. xiv–xv) In the twenty-first century, the phenomenon of “International Airbnb Style” (Heathcote 2020) hints at the homogenization of taste into a minimalist one. The neologism refers to the transition of Airbnb interiors from styles unique to a particular location to “all the same” wherever you go in the world: typically with minimalist furniture, reclaimed wood and industrial lighting. While the styles of IKEA, MUJI, or international hotel chains are centrally created, “air-washed” (ibid.) looks emerged from people making independent decisions, influenced by digital platforms like Instagram where endless images of aspirational, essentially Western, lifestyles circulate.

The examples of the masstige or budget fashion brands pointed out above may evidence that the fashion equivalent of “air-washing” exists. This aesthetic standardization, or gentrification, appears to have created an impression of global class, which divides the world into the mythical category of the minimalist rich and the decorative poor. Such impression is not irrelevant to the structural realities of the fashion system, where high-speed access and circulation of information enable an efficient global supply chain. This “supply chain capitalism” (Tsing 2009, p.150), based on outsourcing and subcontracting, stimulates global standardization while widening gaps between rich and poor. It also creates class-related prejudice about budget fashion consumers: luxury consumers tend to be of an opinion that their tastes are not just aesthetically but also morally superior, when luxury markets are also entangled in a system of global capitalism (Schultz, Paton and Jay 2020).

If fashion can be seen as an endless game of exclusion, it is now played on a global scale, dividing the world into economic, cultural and racial classes. Stealth luxury, minimalist fashion and related narratives in this text address the inherently divisive nature of fashion. The minimalist surface is replete with discriminating marks, highlighting the aspect of fashion as the operation of othering and exclusion, in which we all take part.

NOTES

1. See Carreyrou (2018) for a detailed account of the scandal surrounding Theranos and its opaque practice.
2. Zoran’s first collection “Five easy pieces” (1976) was comprised of a pair of black trousers, a black skirt and three tops. One of most recent examples of luxury capsule wardrobe, WARDROBE.NYC (2017–) specializes in “essentials”: its eight-piece collection comprises of a coat, a blazer, a hoodie, a knit sweater, a dress shirt, a T-shirt and a pair of trousers.
3. See Arnold (2000) for a study focusing on the 1990s minimalist fashion.
4. If the Armani suits of the 1980s signaled the ideal of financial success, the “power vest” of the 2010s deflects the attention away from the same ideal, towards benevolent values such as eco-consciousness or social welfare. Many of the world’s most profitable companies—Google, Facebook, and Apple

among them—allow their employees to dress in jeans and T-shirts all week. This led many of the US financial institutions to follow the “dress-code” of their clients. The phenomenon of the “power vest” exemplifies this trend. The outdoor clothing brand Patagonia’s Nano Puff vest became so popular to those who work in Manhattan and Silicon Valley that Patagonia announced their policy change in 2019: they are co-branding only with “mission-driven companies that prioritize the planet.” Excluded are financial institutions and companies in sectors such as oil, drilling, dam construction, etc. (Notopoulos 2019)

5. Margiela founded Maison Martin Margiela with Jenny Meirens in August 1987. The company was acquired by the Italian group OTB in 2002. Margiela left the Maison in 2008, soon after finishing the Spring–Summer 2009 collection. The company was renamed as Maison Margiela with the appointment of John Galliano as the creative director in 2014.
6. Jenny Meirens used to own a store in Brussels, which represented Comme des Garçons. For Spring–Summer 1998, the Maison and Comme des Garçons presented a joint presentation.
7. Margiela’s influence can be glimpsed via the career path of Nadège Vanhee-Cybulski, who has been the creative director for Hermès womenswear since 2014. Prior to her appointment, Vanhee-Cybulski was trained at Maison Martin Margiela, before moving on to work for Céline (under Philo) and The Row.
8. For instance, Kyoichi Tsuzuki’s photographic collection *Tokyo: a certain style* (1999) portrays the notoriously cramped yet delightfully individualized living spaces of the city.
9. Some of the most well-known examples are Tom Ford at Gucci, John Galliano at Christian Dior, and Alexander McQueen at Givenchy.
10. See Wachenfeldt (2021) for a case study of “The Rich Kids of Instagram,” a social media account and a related TV program.
11. This styling originates from the fact that the Maison could not afford to pay the rights for the models (Holzemer 2019). Nevertheless, it was a successful branding and was staged in various versions.

12. The blank white label was registered, after all, at the Institut National de la Propriété Industrielle (No. 98763828) on 11 December 1998 (Samson 2018, p.156).
13. Other examples include a top made out of Franprix (the French supermarket) plastic bags with the logo on the front bodice (Spring–Summer 1990); wigs made from old fur coats (Fall–Winter 1997–98) displaying their original inscriptions and stamps (Samson 2018, p.74); duvets made into garments (Fall–Winter 1999–2000), with the label of the Italian duvet manufacturer retained (ibid., p.86).
14. The “9” of the exhibition title refers to the nine years over which Margiela has presented eighteen collections; the “4” to the four days it takes the bacteria to grow; and the “1615” to the total hours the exhibition would be on view. (Evans 1998, p.77) The astutely coded title exploits the principle of inverse-exhibitionism while also revealing his preoccupation with the materialization of time.
15. This dress can be viewed in detail on Sotheby’s website:
<https://www.sothebys.com/en/buy/auction/2019/martin-margiela-hors-normes-online/martin-margiela-spring-summer-1996-printemps-ete-4>.
16. Uniqlo collaborated with a series of high-fashion designers known for their minimalist styles, including Jil Sander, Tomas Maier, JW Anderson, Christophe Lemaire and Alexander Wang.

REFERENCES

- Arnold, Rebecca. “Luxury and restraint: minimalism in 1990s fashion.” In *Fashion Business: Theory, Practice, Image*, edited by Nicola White and Ian Griffiths, 167–81. Oxford; New York: Berg, 2000.
- Arnold, Rebecca. “Luxury, luxe, luxus. Redefining fashion for the new millennium.” In *Margiela, The Hermès Years*, 183–93. Belgium: Lannoo, 2018.
- Barthes, Roland. *The Neutral*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2005.
- Bataille, Georges. *The Accursed Share: An Essay on General Economy*. Volume I (Consumption), translated by Robert Hurley. New York: Zone, 1988.

- Baudelaire, Charles. “The painter of modern life (1863).” In *The Painter of Modern Life and Other Essays*, edited by Jonathan Mayne, 1–40. London: Phaidon, 1964.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1984.
- Bourke, Joanna. “The Great Male Renunciation: men’s dress reform in inter-war Britain.” *Journal of Design History* 9, no. 1 (1996): 23–33. DOI: 10.1093/jdh/9.1.23.
- Carreyrou, John. *Bad Blood: Secrets and Lies in a Silicon Valley Startup*. Picador, 2018.
- Coupland, Douglas. *Generation X, Tales for an Accelerated Generation*. London: Abacus, 1997.
- Cunningham, Patricia A. *Reforming Women's Fashion, 1850–1920: Politics, Health, and Art*. Kent, OH; London: Kent State University Press, 2003.
- Debo, Kaat, et al. *Maison Martin Margiela ‘20’: The Exhibition*. Antwerp: MoMu. 2008.
- Debo, Kaat. “Margiela, The Hermès Years.” In *Margiela, The Hermès Years*, 25–60. Belgium: Lannoo, 2018.
- Evans, Caroline. “The Golden Dustman: A critical evaluation of the work of Martin Margiela and a review of Martin Margiela: Exhibition (9/4/1615).” *Fashion Theory* 2, no. 1 (1998): 73–94. DOI: 10.2752/136270498779754470.
- te Duits, Thimo, ed. *La Maison Martin Margiela: (9/4/1615)*. Rotterdam: Museum Boijmans Van Beuningen, 1997.
- Faiers, Jonathan. “Sartorial connoisseurship, the T-shirt and the interrogation of luxury.” In *Critical Luxury Studies: Art, Design, Media*, edited by John Armitage and Joanne Roberts, 177–98. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2017.
- Fields, Jill. *An Intimate Affair: Women, Lingerie, and Sexuality*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2007.
- Flügel, John Carl. *The Psychology of Clothes*. London: Institute of Psychoanalysis; Hogarth Press, 1930. Reprint 1940.

- Friedman, Vanessa. 2018. "Mark Zuckerberg's I'm Sorry Suit." *New York Times*, April 10. <https://nyti.ms/2Hos4s3>.
- Heathcote, Edwin. 2020. "The curse of the Airbnb aesthetic." *Financial Times*, August 21. <https://www.ft.com/content/6996e7f2-7446-43e5-9c31-2606b9e316b7>.
- Holzemer, Reiner, dir. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words*, film. London: Dogwoof, 2019.
- Horyn, Cathy. 1999. "Zoran, the master of deluxe minimalism, still provokes." *New York Times*, April 20. <https://www.nytimes.com/1999/04/20/style/reviews-fashion-zoran-the-master-of-deluxe-minimalism-still-provokes.html>.
- Leive, Cindi. 2015. "Meet the \$9 billion woman." *Glamour*, March 19. <https://www.glamour.com/story/theranos-founder-elizabeth-holmes-career-advice>.
- Menkes, Suzy. 1993. "Simply modern: contrasting looks at luxury for the 1990s." *International Herald Tribune*, September 28. <https://www.nytimes.com/1993/09/28/style/IHT-simply-moderncontrasting-looks-at-luxury-for-the-1990s.html>.
- Mower, Sarah. 2010. "The return to 1990s minimalist fashion." *Telegraph*, September 9. <https://fashion.telegraph.co.uk/news-features/TMG7977307/The-return-to-1990s-minimalist-fashion.html>.
- Notopoulos, Katie. 2019. "Patagonia is refusing to sell its iconic power vests to some financial firms." *BuzzFeed News*, April 2. <https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/katienotopoulos/patagonia-power-vest-policy-change>.
- Partridge, Eric. *Origins: A Short Etymological Dictionary of Modern English*. Routledge, 2006.
- Petrarca, Emilia. 2019. "How to look rich wearing only Uniqlo." *The Cut*, November 15. <https://www.thecut.com/2019/11/how-to-look-rich-wearing-only-uniqlo.html>.
- Phillips, Adam. *The Vulgar: Fashion Redefined*. London: Koenig, 2016.
- Samson, Alexandre. *Martin Margiela: The Women's Collections 1989–2009*. New York: Rizzoli Electa, 2018.

- Schultz, Kai, Elizabeth Paton and Phyllida Jay. 2020. "Luxury's hidden Indian supply chain." *New York Times*, March 11.
<https://www.nytimes.com/2020/03/11/style/dior-saint-laurent-indian-labor-exploitation.html>.
- Semper, Gottfried. "Preliminary remarks on polychrome architecture and sculpture in Antiquity (1834)." In *The Four Elements of Architecture and Other Writings*, translated by Harry Francis Mallgrave and Wolfgang Herrmann, 45–73. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989. Reprint 2010.
- Sennett, Richard. *The Conscience of the Eye*. New York: WW Norton & Company, 1992.
- Simmel, Georg. "Adornment (1908)." In *The Sociology of Georg Simmel*, edited and translated by Kurt H. Wolff, 338–44. Glencoe, IL: Free Press, 1950.
- Simmel, Georg. "The problem of style (1908)," translated by Mark Ritter. *Theory, Culture & Society* 8 (1991): 63–71.
 DOI:10.1177/026327691008003004.
- Simmel, Georg. "The philosophy of fashion (1905)." In *Simmel on Culture: Selected Writings*, edited by David Frisby and Mike Featherstone, 187–205. London: Sage, 1997.
- Steiner, Robert L., and Joseph Weiss. "Veblen revised in the light of counter-snobbery." *Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 9, no. 3 (1951): 263–68. DOI:10.2307/425888.
- Tsing, Anna. "Supply chains and the human condition." *Rethinking Marxism: A Journal of Economics, Culture & Society* 21, no. 2 (2009): 148–76.
 DOI:10.1080/08935690902743088.
- Tsuzuki, Kyoichi. *Tokyo: A Certain Style*. San Francisco, CA: Chronicle, 1999.
- Veblen, Thorstein. *The Theory of the Leisure Class: An Economic Study of Institutions*. New York: Macmillan, 1899. Reprinted with an introduction and notes by Martha Banta. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press, 2007.
- Vinken, Barbara. "Transvesty–travesty: fashion and gender." *Fashion Theory* 3, no. 1 (1999): 33–49. DOI:10.2752/136270499779165617.
- Vogue. "Zoran: the wizard of ease." *US Vogue* 173, no. 3 (1983): 354–59.

Wachenfeldt, Paula von. “The mediation of luxury brands in digital storytelling.” *Fashion Theory*, 25, no. 1 (2021): 99–118.

Wigley, Mark. *White Walls, Designer Dresses: The Fashioning of Modern Architecture*. Cambridge, MA; London, England: MIT Press, 2001.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Mark Zukerberg’s Facebook post ‘First day back after paternity leave. What should I wear?’. Screenshot. Available from: <https://en-gb.facebook.com/zuck/posts/10102616793975691>

Figure 2. The highly gendered aspect of minimalist luxury fashion is exemplified by The Row, of which the name derives from Savile Row tailoring. Screenshot (detail). Available from:

<https://www.therow.com/gb>

Figure 3. Hermès button with six holes, so the stitching forms the letter 'H'. Screenshot. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words* (2019).

Figure 4a and 4b. Maison Martin Margiela label (inside) and visible tacks (outside). Screenshot.
Martin Margiela: In His Own Words (2019).

Figure 5. The white interior of Maison Martin Margiela studio. Photograph by Daniel Stier.

Figure 6. The sock sweater (Maison Martin Margiela. Fall-winter 1991-92). Screenshot. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words* (2019).

Figure 7. The white collection (Maison Martin Margiela. Spring–Summer 1993). Screenshot. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words* (2019).

Figure 8a. Viscose jersey blouse with leather print (Maison Martin Margiela. Spring–Summer 1996). Screenshot. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words* (2019).

Figure 8b. Jersey sheath dress with sequin dress print (Maison Martin Margiela. Spring–Summer 1996). Screenshot. *Martin Margiela: In His Own Words* (2019).